

E-LaaS

Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

CONFERENCE PANEL

**13th International Scientific and Technical Conference Logistic Systems -
Theory and Practice, September 1 - 3, 2024 Warsaw (Poland)**

***Dedicated project panel – project presentation and selected
research highlights***

SUB-REPORT FOR WP6

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Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC).

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European
Commission

Project funding information

E-Laas project is carried out in an international consortium. Project coordinator in Europe: Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden), project coordinator in China: Shanghai University (China), consortium members: Tsinghua University (China), Warsaw University of Technology (Poland), cooperation partners: Stockholms stad, Trafikkontoret (Sweden), ParkUnload (Spain), Metropolis GZM (Poland), Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department (China), Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations (Sweden).

- *The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China*

- *The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency*

- *The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The value of the co-financing is PLN 878,107.00. Project duration 27/04/2023 - 26/04/2026 (36 months).*

I. Aims of the panel

From September 1 to 3, 2024, the 13th International Scientific and Technical Conference "Logistic Systems – Theory and Practice" took place in Warsaw, Poland. This well-known scientific conference, highly regarded among academics and practitioners in Poland, included a dedicated panel focusing on the research project E-Laas (Energy Optimal Urban Logistics As A Service).

The objective of the panel was to present the project's framework, summarize the research findings to date, and discuss selected aspects related to energy optimization in urban logistics systems. The session aimed to facilitate knowledge exchange among participants and gather feedback from the academic community and logistics industry practitioners on the feasibility of implementing the proposed solutions, as well as to explore potential directions for further research within the project.

The panel provided a platform to showcase the project's key achievements and served as an inspiration for advancing research into innovative urban logistics models.

II. Panel agenda

1. Introduction – information about E-Laas
2. Team member presentations:
 - 2.1. Emilian Szczepański, Jakub Murawski, Marianna Jacyna: Energy management in urban logistics (Zarządzanie energią jako element logistyki miejskiej)
 - 2.2. Michał Kłodawski, Jachimowski Roland, Nehring Karol: The impact of intermodal train loading strategies on crane energy consumption (Wpływ strategii załadunku pociągu intermodalnego na zużycie energii przez suwnicę)
 - 2.3. Jan Paszkowski, Emilian Szczepański: Reference zones in the modelling of urban logistics (Rejony wzorcowe w modelowaniu logistyki miejskiej)
 - 2.4. Jakub Murawski, Emilian Szczepański: The problem of EV routing in terms of energy consumption optimization (Zagadnienie trasowania pojazdów elektrycznych z punktu widzenia optymalizacji zużycia energii)
 - 2.5. Michał Kłodawski, Konrad Lewczuk: Microsimulation as a tool for modelling urban Logistics (Mikrosymulacja jako narzędzie modelowania logistyki miejskiej)

III. Attachments

- 1) Presentations
- 2) Conference programme (in Polish)

Attachment 1: Presentations

Presentation - point 2.1

Faculty of Transport
 Warsaw University of Technology

E-Laas panel
 (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)

02.09.2024
 Warsaw, Poland

International Scientific Conference - 2024
Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)

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Logos of funding bodies: European Commission, URBAN EUROPE, NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE POLAND, Swedish Energy Agency.

Logos of consortium members: CHALMERS, URBAN EUROPE, Tsinghua University, Warsaw University of Technology, Stockholm stad, Gdynia Zasklebienska Metropolia, SHANGHAI, PARKUNLOAD, Volvo Group.

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E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)

- **Increasing Importance of Zero-Emission Solutions**
 - > regional, EU, Chinese, and UN directives.
- **Electromobility and Urbanization**
 - > growing urban populations and freight volumes.
 - > charging electric vehicles
 - > energy system management
- **Emergence of New Freight Modes**
 - > electric vehicles, drones, cargo bikes.
 - > challenges in synchronization and urban landscape adaptation.
- **Impact on Urban Logistics Providers**
 - > increased demand for optimization and modularity.
 - > rising importance of space-efficient and fossil-free delivery platforms.

E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)

**Partnership
China-Poland-Sweden**

- Diverse Urban Landscapes
- Cultural and Behavioral Insights
- Sustainability and Innovation

Partnership and a wide range of needs, approaches and points of view will allow the development of unique solutions for urban logistics in E-Laas

**Strategic Consortium:
Leveraging Diversity for Sustainable Logistics Solutions"**

China's Lead in Electric-Vehicle Sales
Demand for EVs and plug-in hybrids has taken off

■ China ■ Europe ■ US ■ Japan ■ Rest of World

Source: BloombergNEF
Note: Europe includes the EU, the UK, and EFTA countries. 2024 onward are forecasts.

Bloomberg

E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)

- ✔ Represent urban logistics missions as logistics flows
- ✔ Define operational (and complementary) energy use in logistics flows
- ✔ Analyze spatio-temporal energy usage in urban logistics missions and perform sensitivity analysis (grid interruption, scalability)
- ✔ Incentivize energy awareness on multiple levels (from customers to authorities)

Create a novel energy-minimizing method from consolidation centers to the customers' doors incentivizing energy savings at each level

Faculty of Transport
Warsaw University of Technology

Emilian Szczepański, Jakub Murawski, Marianna Jacyna

Zarządzanie energią jako element logistyki miejskiej

Energy management in urban logistics

International Scientific Conference - 2024
Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

Agenda - Energy management in city Logistics

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

State of the art

Review of Relevant Projects

This review assessed projects related to E-LaaS, focusing on thematic relevance and potential contributions.

- Assessment of thematically related projects.
- Evaluation of information sources (subpages, websites).
- Classification of reviewed projects.

Databases:

- 1) CORDIS,
- 2) JPI Urban Europe,
- 3) EIT Urban Mobility,
- 4) Interreg,
- 5) EUREKA,
- 6) ERA-Learn,
- 7) National Science Centre (NCN), Poland,
- 8) National Centre For Research and Development (NCBR), Poland and Map of EU grants, Poland

106 projects of potential added value for E-LaaS

General Observations

- 65% of projects have dedicated websites, 55% active.
- 56% of projects provide detailed results.
- Limited availability of source data, primarily within consortiums.
- Only 4 project publish open-source data, but not all data

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

State of the art in E-Laas areas

Review of Relevant Projects

Field of Added Value	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
Last-mile concepts	21	16
Simulation and decision support	9	4
Policy shaping guidelines	7	4
Input data	4	0

Shaping urban logistics policies:

- NOVELOG
- SPROUT
- SULPITER
- Sustainable last mile urban logistics and returns

Methodological:

- LEAD
- SENATOR
- HUPMOBILE
- EUFAL

Parking spots:

- PARKUNLOAD
- ASAP
- S+LOADZ
- Coding the Curbs
- Freight TAILS

E-Laas introduces innovations in the following areas:

- Detailed consideration of the energy problem in logistics operations
- Modeling of social behaviors
- Unique methodological approach
- New solutions and methods for their evaluation in the construction of Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULP) and real implementation

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

State of the art in E-Laas areas

Energy management in urban Logistics - comprehensive review of literature – review publications

The review identifies 38 review articles focusing on four main areas:

Energy Management in Vehicles

- Focus on electric and hybrid vehicles.
- Algorithms and approaches like MPC (Model Predictive Control) for energy optimization.
- Challenges in battery degradation, charging infrastructure, and V2G integration.

Energy-Efficient Logistics

- Implementation of green technologies in logistics.
- Use of electric vehicles, drones, and cargo bikes.
- Review of logistics strategies like cargo consolidation and the integration of public transport.

Optimization of Energy Use

- Strategies for optimizing energy consumption in transportation.
- Analysis of Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) and energy-efficient routing solutions.

Energy Networks and Management

- The impact of urban logistics on energy networks.
- Integration of renewable energy sources with logistics operations.
- Smart grid technologies and their role in managing energy demand from logistics activities.

The analysis emphasizes the need for further research on system-wide energy management in urban logistics, including the integration of logistics activities with urban energy systems

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

State of the art in E-Laas areas

Energy management in urban logistics - comprehensive review of literature – research publications

191 articles from a sample of 9609

microscale

- energy management in means of transport
- charging/discharging vehicle management
- battery management
- storing energy in the vehicle
- storing energy in charging stations

mezoscale

- EV charger location
- Vehicles charging management strategies
- Battery swapping
- V2G and V2V in a systems approach

macroscale

- Impact of EVs on the power grid
- Energy management in the city as a whole or within specific sectors of groups (centralized, decentralized)

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

State of the art in E-Laas areas

SULP in Poland

- ✓ **SUMP** – 19 cities or urban agglomeration in Poland
 - establishment of local consolidation centers
 - creation of dedicated parking spaces for delivery vehicles
 - utilization of low-emission (zero-emission or low-emission) delivery vehicles
 - use of cargo bicycles
 - restriction of heavy-duty vehicle traffic
 - construction of publicly accessible charging stations for zero-emission or low-emission vehicles
 - development of recommendations for the location and operation of parcel lockers
 - utilization of rail transport
 - implementation of soft measures (e.g., collaboration with carriers to develop rational solutions)

- ✓ **POZNAŃ SULP (SULPiTER)**
 - There is no obligation to develop a SULP, unlike a SUMP
 - Currently, there are no official SULPs in Poland
 - Only selected aspects appear in the SUMP to a very limited extent

As can be seen from the preliminary work and state of the art, E-Laas is needed as a new point on the city logistics road map

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

Tools and methods

Microscale

Mezoscale

Makroscale

Energy Management System

- Rule-based
- Optimization based

Software

- AVL Cruise
- Matlab – UDDS - Urban Dynamometer Driving Schedule
- CPLEX
- GAMS
- ANYLOGIC
- FLEXSIM
- PTV VISUM

Datasets

- Urban Transport Roadmaps Tool
- Transportation Secure Data Center (TSDC) - For urban driving cycles
- Next Generation Simulation (NGSIM) program
- U.S. Department of National Renewable Energy Laboratory provides second-by-second driving cycle data
- HBEFA (Handbook on Emission Factors for Road Transport)

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

Reference cases and research scenarios

Delivery of ready-made food on order to individual recipients

Delivery of ready-made boxed meals to individual recipients

Delivery of grocery to individual recipients

Urban delivery of medicines and pharmaceuticals

Package deliveries from hubs on the outskirts of cities to parcel lockers

Package deliveries from hubs on the outskirts of cities to individual customers

B2B goods deliveries – cargo transport between businesses excluding individual consumers

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

A hybrid approach to simulation modelling of urban logistics

1. Macrosimulation - obtaining data on areas, traffic flow distribution, resistance on connections, isolating representative areas for microsimulation

2. Microsimulation - analysis of individual areas (districts, regions) due to different characteristics

3. Macrosimulation - extrapolation of obtained results to the entire area, studying the logistics system in the city (divided into demand segments or as a whole)

4. Scaling - constructing cities from representative fragments, for different sizes and characteristics - depending on the city's characteristics - suggestions for shaping policy

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

Assumption for survey research of Logistics systems stakeholders (WP2)

LP	Survey group – couriers
1	Delivery of ready-made food on order to individual recipients
2	Delivery of ready-made boxed meals to individual recipients
3	Delivery of grocery to individual recipients
4	Package deliveries from hubs on the outskirts of cities to parcel lockers
5	Package deliveries from hubs on the outskirts of cities to individual customers
6	B2B goods deliveries
7	Urban delivery of medicines and pharmaceuticals
Suma 1-7	

LP	Survey group
8	Survey for municipalities/districts
9	Survey for logistics system customers
10	Survey for logistics operators
Suma 7-10	

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For groups 1-7 – Drivers/couriers/delivery workers

Metrics

For developing a profile and assigning to a region and a given research scenario

• Metrics

- Belonging to the surveyed group
- Locality/locality (work area/recipient location)
- Type of goods
- Area of operation (village, suburbs, housing estates, city centers, industrial zones)
- Postal codes of loading/unloading locations
- Means of transport used in delivery, including e.g. refrigerated
- Drive (none, internal combustion, electric, hybrid, plug-in hybrid)
- Model of ownership of the means of transport
- Vehicle service (who is responsible for current service, including refuelling)
- Typical working days (weekdays/weekends)
- Regularity of work (occasionally, daily)
- Type of mobile applications used

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For groups 1-7 – Drivers/couriers/delivery workers

Metrics

For developing a profile and assigning to a region and a given research scenario

Average working day for demand model and simulation model parameterization

• Average working day :

- Total kilometres travelled per day
- Number of working hours per day
- Typical working hours
- Number of loading addresses per day
- Number of daily loadings per day
- Number of delivery addresses per day

Average:

- number of parcels per single delivery location
- number of parcels per day
- share of parcels by size
- distance from the loading point to the delivery point
- vehicle loading time
- waiting time for loading
- travel time between the loading point and the delivery point
- unloading time
- time spent looking for a parking lot/place to stop for unloading
- the daily idle time during working hours
- daily time spent on current vehicle maintenance
- how often the recipient is not at the delivery address
- where do you most often leave the parcel

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For groups 1-7 – Drivers/couriers/delivery workers

Metrics:

For developing a profile and assigning to a region and a given research scenario

Average working day
for demand data and simulation model parameterization

Preferences

Examine current trends and behaviors to map the model logic and parameterize agents in the model

Preferences:

- o Would you change your vehicle for another? (larger/smaller car, bike, other)
- o Would you change for a vehicle with a different power supply?
- o How do you assess the usefulness of electric vehicles in your industry?
- o Would the expansion of urban infrastructure (parking lots, parking spaces dedicated to suppliers, and parking spaces equipped with chargers) affect the delivery process, and how?
- o Would you change your working hours to night/off-peak hours to avoid wasting time sitting in traffic jams?
- o How often do you have trouble finding a space during a delivery?
- o How often are you forced to stop in a prohibited place or on an active lane?
- o What is the most annoying/inconvenient thing during the delivery process?

If an electric vehicle is used :

- o Does the vehicle require recharging during the working day?
- o Does he/she use chargers in the city area - or at the company/home base?
- o Is the availability of chargers sufficient?
- o Are dynamic energy prices a good solution, e.g., one related to the availability of chargers/traffic intensity?
- o Is the vehicle unreliable?

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For group 8 – municipalities, districts

Metrics:

- o City, urban district

Matching the study area to the characteristics of the city/region

Model calibration and scenario mapping for the studied areas

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For group 9 – logistics system customers

Metrics:

- o Town/towns (work area/recipient location)
- o Postal code of place of residence
- o Place of residence (village, suburbs, housing estates, city centres)
- o Gender
- o Age
- o Methods of getting around - own car, public transport, bicycle
- o What deliveries do you use (from groups 1-7)

Matching customers to scenarios and mapping their needs in the demand model

Preferences:

- o what is the preferred - most frequently chosen method of receiving a parcel?
- o what are the problems with the above delivery methods?
- o what are the problems with the delivery of a box diet?
- o What are the problems with couriers delivering food if you have used it?
- o Do you have limited mobility?
- o Average number of parcels received per week
- o Average share of parcels received by size
- o Characteristics of the method of receiving a parcel from parcel lockers/collection points and use: Time limit for reaching the parcel locker, distance from the nearest parcel locker, etc.
- o if you send parcels, in what % share (parcel locker/courier/dispatch point/post office)
- o do you send return parcels to the courier during delivery [always - not at all]
- o how often do you send parcels
- o how many parcels on average during one sending
- o average share of parcels by size
- o do you care about the emission of pollutants related to the delivery of the parcel

Input for demand model and mapping customer behavior in the simulation model logic

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

The assumption for survey research of stakeholders in logistics systems

For group 10 – Logistics operators

- **Metrics:**
 - Town (work area/company location): Postal codes of loading/unloading points
 - Type of goods handled (by groups 1-7)
 - Area of operation (village, suburbs, housing estates, city centers, industrial zones, all of the above)
 - Vehicle fleet - composition
 - Current vehicle ownership model
 - Use of vehicles to transport loads sensitive to ambient temperature (refrigerated, ice-cream, thermal bag, other...)
 - Vehicles drive - share in % (combustion, electric, hybrid, other)
- **Preferences:**
 - Green Vehicle Implementation Plans - Electric Cars, Cargo Bikes, Smaller Delivery Vehicles, Other:?
 - What incentives would convince you to change your fleet to a greener one?
 - What are the main barriers to implementing electric vehicles in your fleet?
 - Would expanding city infrastructure affect the delivery process, and how?
 - How difficult would it be for you to change the delivery method by using transshipment points - microhubs, cargo consolidation centers, using shared services?
 - Preferred vehicle ownership model
 - Does the clean transport zone affect your business, and how?
 - What regulatory preferences should be included in city transport policies?

- Calibration of scenarios and refinement of model parameters for both macro and micro simulations – e.g. modal split, vehicle structure, assessment of emissions and energy consumption, etc.
- Additionally, conclusions for shaping transport policy in SULP

E-Laas – Energy management in urban logistics

Conclusions

Energy system

- Conventional energy sources
- Alternative energy sources (PV, Wind, Water,...)
- Energy distribution
- Energy storage
- Microgrids
- Transport chargers
- Energy system management
- ...

Systems Integration

- V2G, V2V, G2V
- Energy pricing and charger access policy
- Energy grid disruptions
- Energy consumption balancing
 - IoT
 - Data availability
- Policies and regulations
- ...

Logistics system

- Transport means – modal split, vehicle loading strategies, fleet management
 - Logistics infrastructure – Microhubs, PUDO, Distribution, consolidation, returns centres
- Demand and supply organisation (e.g. time windows, route optimisation)
- Economic aspects
- ...

How to organize last mile deliveries taking into account the energy system while meeting social requirements?

Faculty of Transport
 Warsaw University of Technology

Emilian Szczepański, Jakub Murawski, Marianna Jacyna
 Energy management in urban logistics

Thank you for your attention!

International Scientific Conference - 2024
 Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

Presentation - point 2.2

The impact of intermodal train loading strategies on crane energy consumption

Michał Kłodawski, Roland Jachimowski, Karol Nehring

Warsaw University of Technology, Faculty of Transport

E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

Urban Logistics is a branch of logistics dealing with the management, planning and optimization of the flow of goods, services and information in urban areas.

Ensuring efficient and sustainable delivery/shipping of goods to/from consumers, businesses and institutions in cities, while minimizing the negative impact on the environment, traffic and the quality of life of residents.

Last mile delivery (logistics) – deliveries from hubs to recipients, stores

First mile delivery – deliveries from the manufacturer to distribution hubs or warehouses

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Energy-optimal urban logistics:

- Use of low-emission vehicles
- Cargo bikes and foot deliveries, drones, etc.
- Consolidation of deliveries
- Use GPS, IoT, and big data to monitor and optimize delivery routes in real-time
- Determining optimal delivery times
- Efficient returns and waste management to minimize additional transports.
- Automation and digitization
- Using data analytics to accurately forecast demand
- Optimal location of transshipment hubs and process management in these hubs

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

- Cargo Handling Between Different Modes of Transport
- Cargo consolidation allows for better synchronization of freight traffic.
- Reducing environmental pollution – by enabling the use of low-emission transport
- Increased cargo security

The energy efficiency of the terminal is important from the point of view of urban logistics assumptions

Intermodal terminals are increasingly offering:

- Warehousing services for goods, allowing for better inventory management and flexibility to adapt to changing demand.
- Customs service of cargo, etc.

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

Energy efficiency of the intermodal terminal

1. handling equipment

- Handling equipment in terminals:
- STS quay cranes,
- Gantry cranes RMG, RTG
- Wozy wysięgnikowe Reachstacker
- Backhoe trucks
- AGVs, Terminal Tractors

RTG

Power Sources:

- Power grid
- Internal combustion engines
- Batteries

- Winch motor power 250-350kW
- Winch trolley motor power – trolley driven by 2-4 motors, each about 25kW
- Door motor power – the wheels in the gate have their own motors (4-16 motors), each 15-30 kW

2. organization of the operation of these devices

Minimization of the time of engagement of the loading equipment during loading work (e.g. train loading)

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

What affects the loading time of an intermodal train?

1. Distance between the loading track and the container storage location and the nature of the loading cycle (single/double)
2. Number of wagons/length of the train
3. Types of loading units (containers and their dimensions, semi-trailers, swap bodies)
4. Permissible axle loads of wagons
5. Gross Weight of Units
6. Arrangement of intermodal units in the storage yard
7. Configuration of hitch pins on wagons

Objectives of intermodal train loading optimization

Minimization of the distance covered by individual elements of the crane (gate, trolley, winch) considering:

- Configuration of pins on wagons
- Permissible axle loads of wagons
- Gross weight of containers
- Placement of containers in the yard/buffer

Methods for optimising intermodal train loading

- Exact methods
- Metaheuristics, e.g. generic algorithms inspired by biological evolution and others
- Greedy heuristics and neighborhood searches
- Mathematical programming
- **Computer simulation**

SIMULATION MODEL OF CONTAINER TRAIN LOADING

SIMULATION MODEL

assumptions, simulation experiments, results

SIMULATION MODEL- construction

➤ A model developed in the FlexSim

➤ Elements mapped in the simulation model:

- gantry crane,
- container storage yard,
- storage area for containers prepared for loading,
- track strip with wagons ready for loading.

SIMULATION MODEL of a container train loading

➤ PURPOSE OF MODELING:

- estimation of the impact of the method of intermodal train loading on the energy consumption of this process

➤ ASSUMPTIONS:

- the loading front will be operated by an RTG yard crane,
- Containers handled: 20ft, 30ft, 40ft,
- the track strip on which the wagons for loading will be placed has a capacity of 30 wagons,
- Max. The capacity of the wagon is 3 TEU (60 ft). e.g. 20ft+40ft, 30ft+30ft, 20ft+30ft, 3x20ft
- container storage yard capacity, approx. 360 TEU
- containers stored in 2 levels and 3 rows (yard length approx. 485 meters)
- random placement of containers in the storage yard,
- loading takes place from the loading aisle along the track (sorted shipping containers picked up and prepared in advance from the storage yard).

SIMULATION MODEL – mapped process elements

➤ Elements of the loading process mapped in the simulation model:

- Preparing containers for shipment along the right-of-way,

- 1) containers prepared along the track successively from the beginning of the loading track, regardless of the location of a given container in the storage yard

- 2) containers placed along the track at the height of their initial position in the storage yard

SIMULATION MODEL – mapped process elements

➤ Elements of the loading process mapped in the simulation model:

- preparation of containers for shipment along the track lane,
- moving containers from the top of the stacks in order to pick up those at the bottom, the so-called "digging",
- re-inserting containers into the stacks from which they were moved, the so-called "post-digging cleanup".

SIMULATION MODEL – mapped process elements

► Elements of the loading process mapped in the simulation model:

- preparation of containers for shipment along the track lane,
- moving containers from the top of the stacks in order to pick up those at the bottom, the so-called "digging",
- re-inserting containers into the piles from which they were moved, the so-called "post-mining cleanup",
- loading of a train from the storage range according to the logics of the loading process (crane operation):
 - ✓ 1 – successively carriages along the train
 - ✓ 2 – containers along the storage yard (storage lane)
 - ✓ 3 – shortest distance from wagon to container
 - ✓ 4 – the shortest distance from container to wagon
 - ✓ 5 – the shortest distance from the currently reloaded container to the wagon and the currently loaded wagon to the container (the nearest neighbor's algorithm)

SIMULATION MODEL– estimation of energy consumption

Papaioannou, V.; Pietrosanti, S.; Holderbaum, W.; Becerra, V.M.; Mayer, R. Analysis of energy usage for RTG cranes. *Energy* 2017, 125, 337-344.

Day	Working time [h]	Total		Gantry		Hoist		Trolley & losses
		Energy consumption [kWh]	Energy recovery share [%]	Energy consumption [kWh]	Energy recovery share [%]	Energy consumption [kWh]	Energy recovery share [%]	Energy consumption [kWh]
	0h	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	10.3	711.2	57.1	229.47	5.06	440.94	89.00	497.84
2	11.1	748.36	50.1	231.99	4.89	463.99	86.50	523.0
3	11.9	785.53	57.7	243.51	4.47	487.83	83.88	545.9
4	12.7	822.7	51.9	255.04	4.30	510.07	84.10	575.9
5	6.7	439.9	50.8	136.37	2.68	272.74	84.20	307.9
6	7.3	499.2	54.0	154.75	2.89	309.50	72.60	349.4
7	1.4	112.8	49.8	34.97	3.54	69.94	67.10	7.89
8	2.1	160.8	30.2	49.85	2.87	99.69	84.20	11.25

$$E_C = \frac{64,34 \cdot T_P}{3600} + 24,37$$

Total energy consumption:

$$E_C = E_{CX} + E_{CY} + E_{CZ} + E_{CL}$$

E_{CX} - energy consumed by crane gantry motors

E_{CY} - energy consumed by the motors of the winch trolley

E_{CZ} - energy consumed by winch motors

E_{CL} - energy losses

SIMULATION MODEL– estimation of energy consumption

Total energy consumption:

$$E_C = E_{CX} + E_{CY} + E_{CZ} + E_{CL}$$

E_{CX} - energy consumed by crane gantry motors

E_{CY} - energy consumed by the motors of the winch trolley

E_{CZ} - energy consumed by winch motors

E_{CL} - energy losses

Papaioannou, V.; Pietrosanti, S.; Holderbaum, W.; Becerra, V.M.; Mayer, R. Analysis of energy usage for RTG cranes. *Energy* 2017, 125, 337-344.

$$E_{CX} = S_{GEC} \cdot \left(\frac{64,34 \cdot T_X}{3600} + 24,37 \right)$$

S_{GEC}
 S_{TEC}
 S_{HEC} } indicators of energy consumption by the drives of individual crane components

$$E_{CY} = S_{TEC} \cdot \left(\frac{64,34 \cdot T_Y}{3600} + 24,37 \right)$$

T_X
 T_Y
 T_{ZUL}
 T_{ZUE} } Operating times of drives of individual crane components

$$E_{CZ} = S_{HEC} \cdot \left(64,34 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{ZUL} + T_{ZUE}}{3600} \right) + 24,37 \right)$$

SIMULATION MODEL– estimation of energy consumption

Total energy recovered:

$$E_R = E_{RX} + E_{RZ}$$

E_{RX} - Energy recovered during crane gantry operation
 E_{RZ} - energy recovered during winch operation

Papaioannou, V.; Pietrosanti, S.; Holderbaum, W.; Becerra, V.M.; Mayer, R. Analysis of energy usage for RTG cranes. *Energy* 2017, 125, 337-344.

$$E_{RX} = S_{GER} \cdot S_{GEC} \cdot \left(\frac{64,34 \cdot T_X}{3600} + 24,37 \right)$$

$$E_{RZ} = S_{HER} \cdot S_{HEC} \cdot \left(64,34 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{ZDL} + T_{ZDE}}{3600} \right) + 24,37 \right)$$

$\left. \begin{matrix} T_X \\ T_{ZDL} \\ T_{ZDE} \end{matrix} \right\}$ Operating times of drives of individual crane components

SIMULATION MODEL– simulation scenarios

➤ The research included 20 simulation scenarios:

Scenario No.	Crane Operation Logic	Cleaning up after digging	Preparation for shipment	Scenario No.	Crane Operation Logic	Cleaning up after digging	Preparation for shipment
Scenariusz 1	1	NIE	1	Scenariusz 11	1	NIE	2
Scenariusz 2	2	NIE	1	Scenariusz 12	2	NIE	2
Scenariusz 3	3	NIE	1	Scenariusz 13	3	NIE	2
Scenariusz 4	4	NIE	1	Scenariusz 14	4	NIE	2
Scenariusz 5	5	NIE	1	Scenariusz 15	5	NIE	2
Scenariusz 6	1	TAK	1	Scenariusz 16	1	TAK	2
Scenariusz 7	2	TAK	1	Scenariusz 17	2	TAK	2
Scenariusz 8	3	TAK	1	Scenariusz 18	3	TAK	2
Scenariusz 9	4	TAK	1	Scenariusz 19	4	TAK	2
Scenariusz 10	5	TAK	1	Scenariusz 20	5	TAK	2

➤ Each of them was characterized by:

- one of the five loading logics,
- using the cleaning process,
- the method of preparing containers for loading.

SIMULATION MODEL – results

➤ Graphical presentation and analysis of simulation results:

- total energy consumption 80.21 kWh - 141.14 kWh
- increase in energy consumption between the best (20) and the worst (8) scenario approx. 75.96%
- Correlation between operating time and crane energy consumption
- As your total energy consumption increases:
 - ✓ the share of crane gantry working time in the entire crane operating time increases,
 - ✓ the share of energy absorbed by the crane gantry drive in the total energy consumption increases,
 - ✓ The share of recovered energy in relation to total energy consumption is decreasing.

SIMULATION MODEL – results

- Graphical presentation and analysis of simulation results:

In order to reduce energy consumption in the intermodal train loading process, the number of movements and the operating time of the crane gantry should be reduced

Summary and Conclusion

SELECTION OF THE INTERMODAL TRAIN LOADING SCENARIO:

- affects the operating time of the crane and the amount of energy it consumes.
- ✓ reduction of train loading time to approx. 37% (2.94h)
 - ✓ reduction of electricity consumption to approx. 43% (60.49 kWh)
- can lead to increased efficiency and throughput of the entire terminal
- can generate energy savings of up to 43.87 MWh/year (assuming that the terminal handles 3 trains a day, it operates 20 days a month).
- can generate financial savings of up to €25,007.72/year (assuming €0.57/kWh).
- can lead to a reduction in CO2 emissions per year by approx. 27,771.74 kg (assuming that in Poland the production of 1 kWh generates 633g of CO2).

The impact of intermodal train loading strategies on crane energy consumption

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

Michał Kłodawski, Roland Jachimowski, Karol Nehring

Warsaw University of Technology, Faculty of Transport

Presentation - point 2.3

Wydział Transportu
Politechnika Warszawska
Faculty of Transport
Warsaw University of Technology

Model regions in urban
logistics modeling

Project
E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

Jan Paszkowski, Emilian Szczepański

Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice
2024

Agenda

1. Introduction – SULP and SUMP
2. Macroscopic Modeling
3. Microscopic modeling
4. Freight Traffic Research Concept
5. Reference regions
6. Summary

SUMP – Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan

- A strategic plan to meet the needs of residents and businesses in and around cities, for a better quality of life. It builds on existing planning practices and takes into account the principles of integration, participation and evaluation.
- In addition, in addition to standard transport modelling and planning, it places greater emphasis on:
 - A long-term vision of development
 - Social aspect
 - Accessibility and quality of life
 - Integrated development of all modes of transport with a focus on sustainability
 - User participation
 - Evaluation of the solutions used to improve in the future

SULP – Sustainable urban logistics plan

- Expansion of the SUMP Mobility Plan
- Action plan to improve the functioning of freight transport in the metropolitan area
- Assistance in the selection of sustainable logistics policies
- It assumes the following activities:
 - Analysis of the condition of the existing transport of goods and logistics
 - Stakeholder involvement in planning
 - Propose and implement sustainable and cost-effective urban logistics solutions
 - Verification of the benefits of using these solutions
- Involves modelling of cargo flow

SULP – Sustainable urban logistics plan

Examples of sustainable urban logistics solutions

- Designated places for loading and unloading in the city
- Urban transshipment centers
- Transshipment microhubs in city centres
- Entry control and regulation (congestion charge, restriction of entry times, tonnage and vehicle types)
- Green means of transport (electric vehicles, cargo bikes)
- Logistics pooling (joint deliveries to multiple recipients in the city)

Macroscopic Modeling

Supply and demand

- Supply – transport network
 - Nodes: simplified where segments connect
 - Sections: connections between nodes, carrying traffic, along with speed, capacity, etc.
- Demand: Travel demand

Four-stage model

- Travel generation: the demand for travel in the region
- Traffic Cable: Number of trips between regions
- Division of transport tasks: traffic links for individual types of journeys
- Traffic schedule: distribution of journeys on the transport network

Macroscopic Modeling

Macroscopic modeling - stages

- Identification of moving potentials of freight traffic
- Travel motivations (types of travel sources and destinations): warehouses, logistics centers, etc.
- Freight traffic truss
- Peak hours of freight traffic
- Means of transport
- Transport performance in the region

Microscopic modeling

Microscopic modelling of freight traffic

- Accurate network mapping
- Individual representation of each element of the model
- Mapping of logistics behaviors and processes
- Dynamic model

Freight traffic modelling

Microscopic modelling (simulations of selected areas of the city)

- Microscopic models will be developed using the FlexSim tool
- FlexSim is an advanced tool for modeling and simulation of systems and processes
- It enables visualization, analysis and optimization of various operational scenarios, supports in strategic decision-making.
- It offers three-dimensional graphical models of systems - it facilitates the identification of potential problems and improvements
- Widely used tool in industry, logistics, supply chain management

Macroscopic Modeling

Objectives of freight traffic modelling

- Determination of demand for cargo transportation
- Analysis of the division of transport tasks
- Planning new transport infrastructure
- Spatial planning support
- Optimization of urban logistics infrastructure
 - Location of transshipment points
 - Vehicle routes
 - Cargo consolidation
- Reduce noise and emissions
- Improve safety

Freight traffic modelling

The concept of urban freight traffic research

- Macroscopic model dataset
 - Road network and its parameters
 - Traffic volume and type structure
- Mapping of the area in the microscopic model (Flexsim)
 - Mapping of the existing state
 - Modification of logistics processes
 - Change of freight turnover
- Analysis in a macroscopic model
 - Introduction of new transport performance
 - Comparison of the results of the traffic schedule and total transport turnover
- Selection of model regions

Freight traffic modelling

Dataset for Microscopic Model Applications

- Macroscopic model:
 - Supply: nodes and segments with their parameters
 - Demand: Production and attraction of the area, POIs if possible
 - Traffic schedule: Vehicle traffic
- Data GIS, GUS:
 - Location of delivery points
 - Types of logistics customers in the region
- Survey data – transport behaviour:
 - Carriers: type of vehicle, volume of transports, length and duration of driving per day, number of delivery points per vehicle,
 - Customers: frequency and volume of deliveries, preferred date

Freight traffic modelling

Mapping an urban area in a microscopic model (Flexsim)

- A network mapped by a set of segments and nodes;
- Possibility to use the Open Street Map and identify the actual routes of roads between network elements;
- Demand mapping - distributed and networked nodes with a specific demand for goods;
- Supply mapping - scattered and networked objects generating streams of goods;
- Means of transport – the ability to map any means of transport for transporting goods, including pedestrian traffic, bicycle traffic, drones...
- Scenarios – the ability to build simulation scenarios for which the values of decision variables will be automatically changed and the collection of characteristics from the simulation

Freight traffic modelling

Analysis of the results of simulation of scenarios from a microscopic model in a macroscopic model

- Analysis of changes from the original state of the macroscopic model
 - Vehicle Structure by Type
 - Transport performance
- Analysis of traffic distribution results:
 - Traffic
 - Waste of time
 - Energy consumption
 - Exhaust emissions

Reference regions

Objectives of the selection of model regions

- Ability to obtain accurate characteristics using model results for selected areas
- Ability to scale the results of microscopic models

Reference regions

Data used to identify the reference regions

- Data from the macroscopic model:
 - Motivations:
 - Passenger: Home, Work, School, College, Other
 - goods: parking, wholesalers, shops/services, industrial zones, logistics centers, others
 - Movement potentials: production and attraction by motivation
 - Area of the district [km²]
 - District number

Example of pattern regions

- ❖ Data pre-processing – motivation factor
 - Number of trips in motivations taking into account the area of the region
 - A combination of motivations related to:
 - Passengers
 - Cargo
 - Maximum Value Reference
- ❖ Further data processing
 - The sum of motivation factors in the region
 - Contribution of individual motivation factors
- ❖ Comparison of categorization of regions:
 - Manual, based on land use
 - Based on the above parameters

Example of pattern regions

Example of a reference region: center

- Motivation factor
 - Operation: >0.25
 - Other: >0.05
- Number of regions qualified:
 - Manual, based on land use: 12 districts
 - Based on the above parameters: 10 regions
 - Error: 2

Summary

- The concept assumes the use of simulation tools to model logistics in cities
 - Use of the existing macroscopic model along with its extension with additional information about the stakeholders
 - Creating a microscopic model for the analyzed area of the city in order to accurately map the selected solutions
 - Transfer of the results of the micro- model to the macroscopic model
 - Traffic distribution analysis
- Use of reference regions:
 - Microscopic modeling for selected areas
 - Scaling results for the entire analyzed terrain

Further research

- ❖ Reference regions
 - Selecting a set of pattern region types
 - Augmented data analytics
 - Automate parameter matching
 - Determination of parameters for each type of reference regions
- ❖ Urban logistics modelling
 - Construction of microscopic models for reference regions
 - Scaling method to a macroscopic model
 - Analysis of results in a macroscopic model

Model regions in urban logistics modeling

Project

E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency. The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China.

Presentation - point 2.4

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

The problem of EV routing in terms of energy consumption optimization

Jakub Murawski, Emilian Szczepański
Warsaw University of Technology, Faculty of Transport

E-Laas project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency. The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China.

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Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

ENERGY DEMAND

Global energy demand

Source: ONZ Habitat

Energy demand in cities

Source: International Energy Agency

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2024

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2024

3

VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM

- Objective:**
 determining optimal routes for the delivery of cargo from the hub (warehouse) to end customers
- Assumptions:**
- each vehicle carries out one route;
 - the volume of demand for deliveries and the location of customers are known;
 - the payload of the vehicles is limited;
 - The vehicle, after serving all customers, returns to the hub.

ELECTRIC VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM

- Assumptions:**
- deliveries are handled by electric vehicles;
 - vehicles are equipped with batteries;
 - the range of vehicles is determined by the battery capacity and the energy consumption of the vehicle;
 - vehicles leave the hub with a fully charged battery,
 - the battery can be recharged at charging stations;
 - The vehicle at the charging station is always fully charged.

(Conrad, Figliozzi, 2011)
 (Erdoğan, Miller-Hooks, 2012)

EXAMPLES OF EVRP PROBLEMS

EVRP

- EVRP with Partial Recharges
- EVRP with Capacitated Charging Stations
- Multi-Trip EVRP
- EVRP with Time Windows
- EVRP with Stochastic Demand
- Heterogeneous EVRP
- Two-Echelon EVRP
- EVRP with Multiple Technologies
- EVRP with Pickup and Delivery
- EVRP with Battery Swapping Stations
- EVRP with Load-Dependent Discharging
- EVRP with Mixed Fleet
- Collaborative EVRP
- EVRP with Flexible Deliveries
- Dynamic Stochastic EVRP

EVRP PROBLEM CLASSIFICATION

Classification of EVRP problems according to:

- technology and organization of the energy replenishment process,
- type of vehicle fleet,
- the structure of the transport system,
- organization of the supply system,
- customer requirements in terms of delivery time,
- uncertainty of demand reported by customers,
- approach to energy demand.

EVRP ISSUES WITH DIFFERENT TYPES OF VEHICLES

EVRP with Mixed Fleet

An approach that takes into account the possibility of using a mixed fleet of vehicles consisting of internal combustion vehicles and electric vehicles.

(Sassi et al., 2014)

Heterogeneous EVRP

The problem of EVRP assuming the use of vehicles with different characteristics, such as payload, operating costs, battery capacity, energy demand. This approach can be applied to a mixed or uniform fleet of vehicles.

(Sassi et al., 2014)

EVRP PROBLEMS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DIFFERENCES IN THE STRUCTURE OF THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM

Multi-Depot EVRP

In the classic view of the EVRP problem, there is only one warehouse, which is the beginning and the end of all the routes that are calculated. The Multi-Depot EVRP approach allows you to include multiple warehouses (hubs).

(Paz et al., 2018)

EVRP with Time Windows

An approach that assumes that end customers indicate time periods (so-called "time windows") in which deliveries can take place. Deliveries outside the time window are not possible

(Schneider et al., 2014)

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

EVRP ISSUES GIVEN DIFFERENCES IN CHARGING TECHNOLOGIES

Two-Echelon EVRP
Taking into account the two-level nature of the distribution system. Cargo is sent from warehouses to transshipment points (e.g. consolidation centers) and then delivered to customers.
(Jie et al., 2019)

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

EVRP ISSUES GIVEN DIFFERENCES IN CHARGING TECHNOLOGIES

EVRP with Multiple Technologies
Charging points can have different parameters, such as cost and charging time. This approach allows you to include, for example, "fast" chargers in the model.
(Felipe et al., 2014)

EVRP with Battery Swapping Stations
The described model assumes that the batteries in the vehicles will not be charged, but replaced. Battery replacement has a much shorter service time (even a few minutes) than fully charging it. In addition, used batteries removed from the vehicle can be recharged at a more convenient time (e.g. when energy prices are lowest).
(Yang, Sun, 2015)

Systemy Logistyczne: Teoria i Praktyka

EVRP ISSUES GIVEN DIFFERENCES IN CHARGING TECHNOLOGIES

EVRP with Partial Recharges
An approach that assumes that an electric vehicle does not have to be fully charged. Therefore, for each charge, it is necessary to decide on the amount of energy consumed. This approach makes it possible, m.in, to reduce the energy consumed at commercial charging points (outside the storage facility).
(Felipe et al., 2014)

EVRP ISSUES GIVEN DIFFERENCES IN CHARGING TECHNOLOGIES

EVRP with Non-Linear Charging Functions

By default, the vehicle's charge level is a linear function of its charging time. This approach is a significant simplification, because in reality the charging function is nonlinear with respect to time. In general, the charging process can be divided into two stages. Up to approx. 80% of the battery capacity, the current is constant. Then, the vehicle is charged at a constant voltage.

(Montoya et al., 2014)

Source: W. Qinglong, L. Xue, J. Du, K. Fanxin (2016). Smart Charging for Electric Vehicles: A Survey From the Algorithmic Perspective. IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials.

EVRP ISSUES GIVEN DIFFERENCES IN CHARGING TECHNOLOGIES

EVRP with Time Dependent Charging Costs

As you know, electricity costs can fluctuate throughout the day depending on the current demand for electricity (e.g. high energy costs during peak electricity demand hours). The described model takes into account the dynamically changing costs of charging vehicles at charging stations.

(Sassi et al., 2019)

Source: own study

EVRP ISSUES TAKING INTO ACCOUNT DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO ENERGY DEMAND

EVRP with Energy Consumption Uncertainty

A model that assumes that energy demand is stochastic rather than deterministic. It is worth noting that electricity consumption is a parameter that has a decisive impact on the range of the vehicle, and thus the ability to plan a given route. On the other hand, it is a factor that is difficult to estimate, because it depends on many variables.

(Pelletier et al., 2019)

EVRP ISSUES TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE UNCERTAINTY OF CUSTOMER DEMAND

Dynamic EVRP
 The Dynamic EVRP model takes into account the possibility of changing customer demand after the start of the route. Therefore, in the event of a change in demand, the possibility of further implementation of the route is assessed. If the vehicle cannot serve all scheduled customers under the set restrictions, the route is changed.
 (Wang et al., 2021)

EVRP ISSUES TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE UNCERTAINTY OF CUSTOMER DEMAND

Dynamic Stochastic EVRP
 A model that divides customer orders into two sets: deterministic orders (known before the start of the route) and stochastic orders (placed by customers after the start of the route, with a given distribution of the probability of their occurrence).
 (Basso et al., 2022)

COMBINATIONS OF DIFFERENT APPROACHES - EXAMPLE

EVRP - OPTIMIZATION CRITERIA

Optimization criteria used:

- Total Energy Consumption
- Vehicle charging time
- Cost of charging vehicles
- Total length of trails
- Total Delivery Lead Time
- Number of charging stations in use
- number of vehicles used

Direct optimization of energy consumption

Indirect optimization of energy consumption

Failure to address the problem of energy optimisation

ENERGY CONSUMPTION CRITERION

ENERGY CONSUMPTION CRITERION

Most EVRP problems where the optimization criterion is to minimize total energy consumption include:

- aerodynamic losses resulting from air resistance generated by the vehicle,
- losses resulting from rolling resistance (the force preventing the rotational movement of the vehicle wheel on the road surface),
- losses in the drive system understood as the total losses incurred from the moment of "extracting" energy from the battery to their transfer to the torque of the vehicle's wheels,
- loss due to changes in speed (energy required to accelerate the vehicle) and changes in terrain (energy required to climb grades).

Relatively few re-analysed EV routing takes into account the:

- additional losses related to the use of other vehicle systems (e.g. air conditioning, heating, battery temperature control systems),
- changes in battery efficiency due to ambient temperature.

SOLUTION METHODS

Exact methods	Heuristic methods	Combinations of several methods	Machine Learning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • branch-and-price • Abranch-price-and-cut • Column Generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iterated Local Search • Variable Neighborhood Search <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search • Simulated Annealing • Memetic Algorithm • Ant algorithms • Genetic algorithms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combination of Tabu Search and VNS • Combination of ALNS and Column Generation • Combination of ILS and Heuristic Concentration • Combination of ILS and branch-and-cut algorithm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforcement Learning • Safe Reinforcement Learning

CONSIDERATION OF OTHER MODES OF TRANSPORT

Vehicles with split cargo space

Cargo bikes

Drones

A combination of drones and delivery vehicles

Conclusions

- Current trends in the routing area:
 - taking into account stochastic (e.g. uncertainty of transport demand) and dynamic (e.g. change in transport demand after route planning),
 - Formulation of increasingly complex optimization models that take into account specific requirements related to a given area of application (e.g. pharmaceutical sector, use of cargo bikes)
 - use of artificial intelligence to solve EVRP problems, including machine learning methods;
- Interesting research issues that could be taken into account in the future in the problem of routing from the point of view of energy optimization are:
 - taking into account the influence of the driver's driving style, with particular emphasis on the process of energy recuperation during braking,
 - Inclusion of vehicle-to-grid technology
 - inclusion of autonomous vehicles,
 - Taking into account the optimal charging time from the point of view of the constraints of the local energy system.

Thank you for your attention

Presentation - point 2.5

Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

Microsimulation as a tool for modeling urban logistics

Mikrosymulacja jako narzędzie modelowania logistyki miejskiej

E-Laas project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/VS1B/00134). The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency. The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China.

Michał Kłodawski
 Konrad Lewczuk

Systemy Logistyczne Teoria i Praktyka
 1-3.09.2024 Warsaw, Poland

International Scientific Conference - 2024

1

Modeling of deliveries in the city

Modelling of deliveries in the city

Difficulties related to modelling and simulation of urban logistics

- Intertwining **passenger** and **cargo** flows
- **Interactions between modes** of passenger and freight, individual and public transport
- **Dense traffic** conditions
- **Parcel and retail** deliveries (last mile)
- **Differentiated actors**, including individuals and organizations
- **Urban space** and architecture as a critical component
- **Weather**
- Social behaviours and technical culture
- IT and ITS support
- Specific local conditions
- Sustainability
- Complexity of urban systems
- Data quality and availability
- Simulation realism

Models of transport networks

- Summarized material flows
- General flow patterns and resistance functions
- Focus on the single mode of transport
- Limited number of factors

Models of city logistics

- Individual packages
- Individual decisions
- Multimodality and modal shifts
- A large number of different factors

FlexSim vs PTV VISUM – Modeling of deliveries in the city

- **FlexSim** for detailed operational analysis and micro-simulation of processes in logistics and production systems
- **PTV Visum** for macro-simulation in transport planning and analysis at the urban and regional levels

Advanced simulation and modelling tools, but...

- **for use in various contexts**
- **having different strengths**

FlexSim vs PTV VISUM – similarities and differences

Purpose

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stochastic, discrete simulation • Modelling of internal material flows and decision processes • Logistics, transport, production, warehouse and industrial processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deterministic models • Modelling and planning of transport systems at the strategic level • Traffic analysis, public transport, urban mobility management and transport infrastructure planning • Large scale systems

Scale of simulation

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microsimulations accurately reproduce processes at a detailed level • Short-term planning • Processes at the operational level, work optimization, resources management, efficiency or capacity analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Macrosimulation (scale of entire cities, regions or countries). • Long-term planning • Traffic simulation, optimization of public transport routes and assessment of the impact of spatial development plans on the transport system

FlexSim vs PTV VISUM – similarities and differences

Modelling and visualization

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced 3D modelling • Accurate visualization of processes and objects • Visual flow analysis • Focus on the particular flow-items 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualization for data analysis • Maps with 2D representation of traffic flows, congestion and analysis results • Visualization without details and not interactive • Focus on the streams of flow-items

User interface

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object-based 3D modeling • Drag and drop elements to create complex processes using a graphical user interface • Intuitive for users who need a visual representation of processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interface for data analysis • Working with maps and charts • Analytical tools with 2D representations

FlexSim vs PTV VISUM – similarities and differences

Users

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing industry, logistics • Warehouse managers, healthcare, project management • Users are typically process engineers, production managers, logisticians and operational analysts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation planning bodies, traffic engineers, local government units, mobility consultants and transportation infrastructure planning organizations

Analysis and optimization

FlexSim	PTV Visum
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced operational analysis tools • „What-if“ analyse, optimization of production and logistics processes • Detailed analysis of cycle times, resource utilization and operational costs • Algorithms and procedures – Process Flow Logic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic analysis, road traffic modeling, optimization of transport networks, forecasting transport demand and assessment of the impact of transport policy on mobility in cities and regions • Four-stage traffic model and resistance functions

FlexSim as a tool for urban logistics simulation

3D visualization

Realistic 3D models, which facilitates the visualization of logistics processes in the urban environment

„What-if“ analyse

Studying various decision strategies, such as optimization of delivery routes, resource management, analysis of bottlenecks in loading and unloading areas, analysis of access to vehicle charging stations, minimizing energy consumption, or minimizing environmental impact etc.

Optimization of processes

Identification of bottlenecks in the urban logistics network and optimization of processes, which can lead to shortening delivery times, reducing costs and improving the efficiency of the delivery system

FlexSim as a tool for urban logistics simulation

Flexibility and scalability

Can be adapted to various sizes and types of logistics systems, from small local operations to complex, distributed urban networks

Integration with real data

Integration with real operational data, including direct access to databases

Agent based decision making

Agent mechanisms to reflect distributed user decisions

External decision making mechanisms

Possibility of moving decision-making centres outside the model to implement advanced decision-making systems, e.g. based on artificial intelligence/machine learning methods

FlexSim as a tool for urban logistics simulation

Built-in additional tools and research methods

- Opti-Quest (solver)
- **Virtual Reality** for direct interaction with the model
- **ExpertFit** (data distribution analysis)
- **Statistics** (statistical data analysis, SQL)
- **FlexScript** (dedicated environment for coding complex and non-standard processes)
- **Open Street Map** and GIS module
- **Digital twin/shadow** capability

Microsimulation models for urban logistics

- **Limited area of analyse – projection of local results to global models** (e.g. PTV Visum)
- A network mapped using a set of **sections and nodes**
- **Open Street Map** to identify actual road routes between network elements and for **infrastructure modeling (including parking lots, charging stations etc.)**
- **Demand mapping** – distributed and connected to the network nodes with a specific demand for goods (*individual recipients, parcel lockers, shops, restaurants, companies, etc.*)
- **Supply mapping** – distributed and connected facilities generating flows of goods (*individuals, enterprises, parcel lockers, hubs*);
- **Means of transport** – the ability to map any means of transport for transporting goods, including pedestrians, bicycles, drones, and their interactions.
- **Simulation scenarios** for which the values of decision variables will be automatically changed and collecting characteristics from the simulation (e.g. change in network congestion, change in demand and supply over time, hourly peaks)
- **Decision making** – Internal algorithmization or external decision-making mechanisms

Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

E-Laas project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency. The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of Chi...

URBAN EUROPE

NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE
POLAND

Systemy Logistyczne Teoria i Praktyka
1-3.09.2024 Warsaw, Poland

Thank you!

Michał Kłodawski
Konrad Lewczuk

Attachment 2: Conference programme (in Polish)

Program konferencji

1 – 3 września 2024, Warszawa

Organizator: **Wydział
Transportu** www.LSTP.pw.edu.pl
POLITECHNIKA WARSZAWSKA

Patronat:

Rektor
Politechniki Warszawskiej

Komitet Transportu
Polskiej Akademii Nauk

Polskie Towarzystwo
Logistyczne

PROGRAM RAMOWY

Niedziela, 1 września 2024 r.

16.00 – 20.00 Rejestracja uczestników / Registration

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

9.00 – 9.15	Otwarcie konferencji / Conference opening	Sala: Scherzo	
9.15 – 11.20	Sesja plenarna I / Plenary session I	Sala: Scherzo	s. 4
11.20 – 11.40	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
11.40 – 13.30	Sesja plenarna II / Plenary session II	Sala: Scherzo	s. 4
14.00 – 15.00	Lunch		
15.15 – 16.45	Sesja I.1 <i>Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 1</i>	Sala: Scherzo	s. 5
	Sesja I.2 <i>Elektromobilność i zrównoważony rozwój systemów transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Sala: Ballada	s. 5
	Sesja I.3 <i>Czynnik bezpieczeństwa w systemach transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Sala: Sonata	s. 6
16.45 – 17.00	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
17.00 – 18.15	Sesja II.1 <i>Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 2</i>	Sala: Scherzo	s. 6
	Sesja II.2 <i>Efektywna energetycznie logistyka jako usługa miejska (panel projektu E-laas)</i>	Sala: Ballada	s. 7
	Sesja II.3 <i>Problemy konstrukcyjne w systemach logistycznych</i>	Sala: Sonata	s. 7
18.30 – 19.15	Sesja plakatowa / Poster session	Sala: Etiuda	s. 8, 9
20.00	Uroczysta kolacja / Gala dinner		

Wtorek, 3 września 2024 r.

9.00 – 10.30	Sesja III.1 <i>Problemy transportu kolejowego w XXI w.</i>	Sala: Scherzo	s. 10
	Sesja III.2 <i>Problemy optymalizacyjne systemów transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Sala: Ballada	s. 10
	Sesja III.3 <i>Problemy decyzyjne i diagnostyczne w systemach logistycznych</i>	Sala: Sonata	s. 11
10.30 – 10.45	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
10.45 – 12.00	Sesja plenarna III / Plenary session III	Sala: Scherzo	s. 11
12.00 – 12.30	Zamknięcie konferencji / Conference closing	Sala: Scherzo	

PRZEWODNICZĄCY SESJI

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

Sesja plenarna I		Paweł Drożdziel, Piotr Fołęga
Sesja plenarna II		Marianna Jacyna, Jerzy Merkisz
Sesja I.1	<i>Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 1</i>	Marek Karkula, Renata Żochowska
Sesja I.2	<i>Elektromobilność i zrównoważony rozwój systemów transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Iwona Grabarek, Dorota Burchart
Sesja I.3	<i>Czynnik bezpieczeństwa w systemach transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Tomasz Jałowiec, Waldemar Mironiuk
Sesja II.1	<i>Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 2</i>	Agnieszka Merkisz-Guranowska, Adam Rosiński
Sesja II.2	<i>Efektywna energetycznie logistyka jako usługa miejska (panel projektu E-laas)</i>	Emilian Szczepański
Sesja II.3	<i>Problemy konstrukcyjne w systemach logistycznych</i>	Jarosław Korzeb, Marcin Chrzan
Sesja plakatowa		Dariusz Pyza, Andrzej Świdorski

Wtorek, 3 września 2024 r.

Sesja III.1	<i>Problemy transportu kolejowego w XXI w.</i>	Piotr Gołębiowski, Jakub Młyńczak
Sesja III.2	<i>Problemy optymalizacyjne systemów transportowych i logistycznych</i>	Anna Borucka, Mariusz Izdebski
Sesja III.3	<i>Problemy decyzyjne i diagnostyczne w systemach logistycznych</i>	Elżbieta Macioszek, Jolanta Żak
Sesja plenarna III		Jacek Pielecha, Konrad Lewczuk

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

9.15 – 11.20 Sesja plenarna I

Przewodniczący: Paweł Drożdziel, Piotr Folęga

Sala: Scherzo

Wystąpienie przedstawicieli przemysłu oraz spółek i podmiotów rynku transportowego i logistycznego

Tomasz Jałowicz

Bezpieczeństwo wojskowych obiektów logistycznych
Security of military logistics facilities

Rafał Burdzik

Zastosowanie innowacyjnych badań w poszukiwaniu wsparcia bezpieczeństwa transportu
Application of innovative research in the search for transport safety support

Waldemar Mironiuk, Krystian Buszman

Wykorzystanie zaburzeń pola magnetycznego do obserwacji ruchu obiektów pływających jako element bezpieczeństwa systemu logistycznego
Title of the Using magnetic field disturbances to monitor the movement of floating objects as a security element of the logistics system

Teresa Abramowicz-Gerigk, Zbigniew Burciu

Czynnik ludzki w eksploatacji i zarządzaniu statkiem autonomicznym
The human factor in operation of an autonomous ship

Marek Idzior

Implikacje rozwoju infrastruktury elektroenergetycznej na elektromobilność rynku pojazdów samochodowych w Polsce
Implications of the development of electricity infrastructure on the electromobility of the motor vehicle market in Poland

11.40 – 13.30 Sesja plenarna II

Przewodniczący: Marianna Jacyna, Jerzy Merkisz

Sala: Scherzo

Piotr Pryciński, Piotr Pielecha, Jarosław Korzeb, Jacek Pielecha, Mariusz Kostrzewski

Emisja zanieczyszczeń powietrza pojazdów osobowych w Polsce w aspekcie oddziaływania pojazdów na środowisko
Air pollutant emissions from passenger cars in Poland in terms of the impact of vehicles on the environment

Jerzy Duda, Iwona Skalna, Marek Karkula, Piotr Kisielewski

Strategie ładowania autobusów elektrycznych w planowaniu transportu publicznego
Electric bus charging strategies in public transport planning

Dorota Burchart, Marcin Staniek, Piotr Folęga

Zarządzanie śladem węglowym w systemie logistycznym
Carbon footprint management in the logistics system

Robert Szczur, Anna Borucka

Bezpieczeństwo systemu transportowego Sił Zbrojnych Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej w aspekcie rozwoju elektromobilności
Safety of the transport system of the Polish Armed Forces in the aspect of the development of electromobility

Marek Bauer, Piotr Kisielewski

Optimalizacja czasu przejazdu dla potrzeb budowy realistycznych rozkładów jazdy w miejskim transporcie zbiorowym
Optimization of trip times for purpose of building realistic timetables in urban public transport

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.1: Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 1

Przewodniczący: Marek Karkula, Renata Żochowska

Sala: Scherzo

Wojciech Miechowicz, Marcin Kiciński, Izabela Miechowicz, Agnieszka Merkiż-Guranowska

Wpływ częstotliwości połączeń na atrakcyjność regionalnego transportu autobusowego

The impact of frequency on attractiveness of the regional bus transport

Róża Wawryszczuk, Ewa Kardas-Cinal

Badania komfortu jazdy w miejskim transporcie szynowym

Study of Ride Comfort in Urban Rail Transport

Maciej Bieńczyk, Szymon Fierek, Wojciech Miechowicz, Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski Jacek Wilczkowiak

Metodyka budowy referencyjnej bazy przystanków autobusowych na przykładzie Wielkopolski - pilotaż w Powiecie Poznańskim i Mieście Poznaniu

Methodology for building a consistent database of bus stops on the example of Wielkopolska - pilot in Poznań county and the city of Poznań

Marcin Kiciński, Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski

Zezwolenia i zaświadczenia w autobusowym transporcie regularnym w Polsce: ocena i analiza jakości informacji

Permits and certificates in public bus transport in Poland: assessing the quality of information

Piotr Soczówka, Aleksander Sobota, Renata Żochowska

Inwentaryzacja infrastruktury przystankowej w publicznym transporcie zbiorowym a problem skali

Inventory of the stop infrastructure of public transport vs. the problem of the scale

15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.2: Elektromobilność i zrównoważony rozwój systemów transportowych i logistycznych

Przewodniczący: Iwona Grabarek, Dorota Burchart

Sala: Ballada

Marek Pawlik, Renata Barcikowska

Bariery i szanse dla bezpiecznego wykorzystania pojazdów wodorowych w transporcie kolejowym; udział Instytutu Kolejnictwa w projekcie FP4Rail4EATR

Barriers and opportunities for the safe use of hydrogen vehicles in rail transport; Participation of The Railway Research Institute in the FP4Rail4EATR project

Cezary Balewski, Joanna Gawenda, Norbert Chamier-Gliszczyński

Planowanie i ocena elektromobilności w miejskich systemach transportowych

Planning and assessment of electromobility in urban transport systems

Patryk Żuchowicz, Konrad Lewczuk

Zastosowanie uniwersalnego środowiska symulacyjnego z warstwą VR do badań nad bezpieczeństwem pracy

Application of a universal simulation environment with a VR layer for occupational safety research

Iwona Grabarek, Sylwia Bęczkowska, Konrad Lewczuk, Zuzanna Zysk, Patryk Żuchowicz

Wykorzystanie wirtualnej rzeczywistości do analizy ergonomicznych rozwiązań w intralogistyce: badania porównawcze z zastosowaniem systemu analizy kinematyki ruchu

The use of virtual reality for ergonomic analysis in intralogistics: a comparative study utilizing motion kinematics analysis systems

Marcin Chrzan, Tomasz Ciszewski, Waldemar Nowakowski, Mieczysław Kornaszewski

Zastosowanie protokołu SNMP dla zdalnego audytu komputerów wykorzystywanych w zadaniach transportowych

Application of SNMP protocol for remote audit of computers used in transport tasks

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.3: Czynniki bezpieczeństwa w systemach transportowych i logistycznych

Przewodniczący: Tomasz Jałowicz, Waldemar Mironiuk

Sala: Sonata

Ireneusz Celiński, Marcin Staniek

Wykorzystanie technologii LoRa jako alternatywy dla GPS w nawigacji pojazdu górskiego przeznaczonego dla osób o szczególnych potrzebach

The use of LoRa technology as an alternative to GPS in the navigation of a mountain vehicle intended for people with special needs

Grzegorz Sobiecki, Anna Borucka

Ciężkość wypadków w Polsce na tle państw europejskich

Severity of accidents in Poland compared to European countries

Dariusz Pyza, Krzysztof Firląg, Tomasz Krukowicz, Piotr Woźnica

Metoda wyboru odcinków sieci kolejowej do pilotażowych badań zagrożenia ze strony roślinności

Method for selecting railway network sections for vegetation hazard studies

Rafał Burdzik, Dawid Simiński

Badania zachowań pieszych i kierowców w otoczeniu przejść dla pieszych w aspekcie implementacji rozwiązań zwiększających bezpieczeństwo niechronionych uczestników ruchu drogowego

Studies of pedestrians and drivers' behavior around pedestrian crossings in the aspect of implementing solutions to increase the safety of vulnerable road users

Rafał Burdzik, Wongelawit Chema

Analiza porównawcza parametrów ewolucji epidemii i zarządzania ryzykiem epidemicznym w transporcie (12.2019 - 01.2024)

Comparative Analysis of Epidemic Evolution Parameters and Epidemic Risk Management in Transport (12/2019 - 01/2024)

17.00 – 18.15 Sesja II.1: Problemy transportu zbiorowego cz. 2

Przewodniczący: Agnieszka Merkisz-Guranowska, Adam Rosiński

Sala: Scherzo

Katarzyna Pietrzyk-Wiszowaty

Rosnące koszty jako wyzwanie dla branży transportu drogowego w Polsce

Rising costs as a challenge for the road transport industry in Poland

Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski, Michał Wojtal, Jeremi Rychlewski, Wojciech Miechowicz

Metoda oceny poziomu dostępności systemów publicznego transportu zbiorowego dla osób o ograniczonej mobilności

Method for assessing the level of accessibility of public transport systems for persons with reduced mobility

Aleksander Sobota, Renata Żochowska, Marianna Jacyna

Wpływ zmiany modelu organizacji rynku usług przewozowych na niezawodność w publicznym transporcie zbiorowym

The influence of a change in the organization of the transport services market model on reliability in public transport

Piotr Kisielewski, Adam Redmer, Szymon Fierek, Jacek Oblaza

Optymalizacja sekwencyjna zadań pojazdów i kierowców w miejskim transporcie zbiorowym

Sequential Optimization of Vehicle and Driver Scheduling in Urban Public Transport

Krzysztof Drewniok, Aleksander Sobota

Wpływ infrastruktury drogowej na czasy przejazdów odcinków międzyprzystankowych – metodyka i wybrane wyniki

The impact of road infrastructure on travel times of inter-stop sections - methodology and selected results

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

**17.00 – 18.15 Sesja II.2: Efektywna energetycznie logistyka jako usługa miejska
(panel projektu E-laas)**

Przewodniczący: Emilian Szczepański

Sala: Ballada

Michał Kłodawski, Jachimowski Roland, Nehring Karol

Wpływ strategii załadunku pociągu intermodalnego na zużycie energii przez suwnicę
The impact of intermodal train loading strategies on crane energy consumption

Jan Paszkowski, Emilian Szczepański

Rejony wzorcowe w modelowaniu logistyki miejskiej
Reference zones in the modelling of urban logistics

Emilian Szczepański, Jakub Murawski, Marianna Jacyna

Zarządzanie energią jako element logistyki miejskiej
Energy management in urban logistics

Jakub Murawski, Emilian Szczepański

Zagadnienie trasowania pojazdów elektrycznych z punktu widzenia optymalizacji zużycia energii
The problem of EV routing in terms of energy consumption optimization

Michał Kłodawski, Konrad Lewczuk

Mikrosymulacja jako narzędzie modelowania logistyki miejskiej
Microsimulation as a tool for modelling urban logistics

17.00 – 18.15 Sesja II.3: Problemy konstrukcyjne w systemach logistycznych

Przewodniczący: Jarosław Korzeb, Marcin Chrzan

Sala: Sonata

Łukasz Konieczny, Piotr Pelechaty

Metody drganiowe z wymuszeniem kinematycznym stosowane do oceny stanu technicznego układu zawieszenia pojazdu samochodowego
Vibration methods with kinematic excitation used to assess the technical condition of the suspension system of a car vehicle

Andrzej Gągorowski

Optymalizacja struktury tłumika układu wylotowego silnika spalinowego
Optimization of the muffler structure in the exhaust system of the combustion engine

Marcin Jacek Kłos, Marcin Staniek, Grzegorz Sierpiński

Góry bez barier – metoda lokalizacji infrastruktury towarzyszącej w celu realizowania podróży przez osoby o szczególnych potrzebach z zastosowaniem specjalistycznego pojazdu terenowego
Mountain without barriers - a method of locating supporting infrastructure for travel by persons with special needs using a specialised off-road vehicle

Grzegorz Wojnar, Łukasz Konieczny, Rafał Burdzik, Krzysztof Filipowicz, Andrzej Norbert

Wieczorek, Mariusz Kuczaj

Zmniejszenie aktywności drganiowej przenośnika zgrzeblowego
Reduce of vibroactivity of the scraper conveyor

Przemysław Niewiadomski, Agnieszka Merkiż-Guranowska

Doskonalenie procesu wytwarzania części i podzespołów pojazdów i środków transportu rolniczego - analiza trendu wdrażanych innowacji
Improving the process of manufacturing parts and components of agricultural vehicles and means of transport - analysis of the trend of implemented innovations

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

18.30 – 19.15 Sesja plakatowa

Przewodniczący: Dariusz Pyza, Andrzej Świdorski

Sala: Etiuda

Grzegorz Sierpiński, Marcin Staniek, Marcin Jacek Klos

Zużycie energii przez pojazd do turystyki górskiej
Energy consumption of a mountain tourism vehicle

Weronika Pegielska, Maciej Szkoda

Koszt cyklu istnienia w ocenie efektywności środków transportu miejskiego
Life Cycle Cost in Assessing the Efficiency of Urban Transport Systems

Elżbieta Macioszek

Badania w zakresie wpływu pojazdów ciężkich na parametry psychotechniczne kierowców na rondach turbinowych
Research on the impact of heavy vehicles on the psychotechnical parameters of vehicle drivers on turbo roundabouts

Piotr Folega, Dorota Burchart, Marcin Staniek, Radim Lenort

Znaczenie metod oceny cyklu życia w strategii rozwoju zrównoważonego transportu
The importance of life cycle assessment methods in the sustainable transport development strategy

Jolanta Żak, Piotr Gołębiowski, Małgorzata Zysińska

Ocena realizacji usług przez przedsiębiorstwa z branży TSL z zastosowaniem liczb przedziałowych
Evaluation of the performance of services by TSL companies using interval numbers

Piotr Franke, Piotr Soczówka, Michał Lasota, Renata Żochowska

Rozmieszczanie stacji ładowania pojazdów elektrycznych z punktu widzenia samorządów
Deployment of electric vehicle charging stations from the perspective of local authorities

Michał Lasota, Czesław Wojdat, Arkadiusz Pietrzak

Ryzyko wystąpienia zdarzeń niebezpiecznych w przewozach ładunków ponadnormatywnych
The risk of dangerous incidents in the transportation of oversize cargoes

Paweł Gołda, Mariusz Izdebski, Justyna Tomaszewska, Szymon Świergolik

Modelowanie systemów transportu wojskowego z wykorzystaniem procesów Semi-Markowa
Modelling military transportation systems using Semi-Markov processes

Paweł Gołda, Krzysztof Cur, Mariusz Zieja, Karol Przanowski, Szymon Świergolik

Prognozowanie Transportu Lotniczego Towarów pomiędzy Polską a Niemcami z wykorzystaniem modelu SARIMA

Forecasting Air Transport of Goods between Poland and Germany using the SARIMA model

Ilona Gołda-Jacyna, Paweł Gołda, Karol Przanowski, Justyna Tomaszewska, Szymon Świergolik

Prognozowanie opóźnień lotów za pomocą kart scoringowych
Forecasting flight delays using scorecards

Aleksandra Zabielska, Marianna Jacyna

Model decyzyjny doboru technologii przepływu ładunków przez obiekty logistyczne
Decision-making model for selecting the technology of cargo flow through logistics facilities

Piotr Gołębiowski, Jolanta Żak, Tomasz R. Waśniewski, Małgorzata Zysińska

Ocena odporności sieci transportowej na zmiany popytu na usługi przewozowe
Evaluation of the resilience of the transport network to changes in demand for transport services

Mirosław Siergiejczyk, Adam Rosiński

Bezpieczeństwo fizyczne systemów IT w systemach transportowych
Physical security of IT systems in transport systems

Poniedziałek, 2 września 2024 r.

18.30 – 19.15 Sesja plakatowa

Przewodniczący: Dariusz Pyza, Andrzej Świdorski

Sala: Etiuda

Marcin Staniek, Dorota Burchart, Piotr Folęga

Raportowanie zrównoważonego rozwoju w branży logistycznej
Sustainability reporting in the logistics industry

Patrycja Guzanek, Anna Borucka

Koncepcja doskonalenia procesu harmonogramowania dostaw na przykładzie przedsiębiorstwa specjalizującego się w sprzedaży kosmetyków
The concept of improving the delivery scheduling process on the example of a company specializing in the sale of cosmetics

Ewelina Sendek-Matysiak

Ocena wykorzystania pojazdów z różnym typem napędu w systemach carsharingu
The assessment of the use of vehicles with different types of drive-in carsharing systems

Jerzy Bogdański, Mariusz Izdebski

Wybrane problemy oceny wydatku energetycznego autobusów elektrycznych w przedsiębiorstwie transportu miejskiego
Selected problems of evaluating the energy expenditure of electric buses in a public transport company

Patryk Jurkowski, Aleksander Figielski

Rozwój Grodziskich Przewozów Autobusowych, czyli szansa na walkę z wykluczeniem transportowym
Development of Grodzisk Bus Transport - a chance to fight against transport exclusion

Wtorek, 3 września 2024 r.

9.00 – 10.30 Sesja III.1: Problemy transportu kolejowego w XXI w.

Przewodniczący: Piotr Gołębiowski, Jakub Młyńczak

Sala: Scherzo

Szkopiński Janusz

Problematyka prowadzenia ruchu pociągów w czasie rzeczywistym
Problems of running train traffic in real time

Jakub Młyńczak, Szymon Surma

Przejazd kolejowy w aspekcie prawa budowlanego i prawa o ruchu drogowym
Level crossings against Construction Law and Road Traffic Law

Michał Steuer, Martin Krzykowski, Rafał Burdzik, Andrzej Kochan

Systemy pozycjonowania satelitarnego w zastosowaniach przewoźników kolejowych do śledzenia taboru kolejowego – źródła danych satelitarnych w kontekście badań
Satellite positioning systems in railway operators' applications for tracking rolling stock - satellite data sources in the context of research

Martin Krzykowski, Michał Steuer, Rafał Burdzik, Piotr Gołębiowski

Wpływ parametrów infrastruktury kolejowej i przepustowości linii kolejowych na średnią prędkość pojazdów szynowych w transporcie kolejowym
Effect of rail infrastructure parameters and line capacity on the average speed of rail vehicles in rail transport

Jacek Kukulski, Andrzej Ratkiewicz

Koncepcja szyny kolejowej do zastosowania w torze bezstykowym
Railway rail concept for use in a contactless track (CWR)

9.00 – 10.30 Sesja III.2: Problemy optymalizacyjne systemów transportowych i logistycznych

Przewodniczący: Anna Borucka, Mariusz Izdebski

Sala: Ballada

Stanisław Ejdyś

Transport drogowy w Polsce w obliczu nowych wyzwań
Road transport in Poland facing new challenges

Emilia T. Skupień

Modele dojrzałości w ocenie systemów transportowych – przegląd literatury
Maturity models in the assessment of transport systems - a literature review

Iwona Skalna, Jerzy Duda, Marek Karkula

Szacowanie danych natężenia ruchu i czasów obsługi dla problemu wielokryterialnego trasowania pojazdów
Traffic and service data estimation for multi-objective vehicle routing problem

Karol Nehring, Roland Jachimowski

Optymalizacja aerodynamiki pociągu kontenerowego jako czynnik poprawy bezpieczeństwa i efektywności w transporcie intermodalnym
Optimization of the aerodynamics of a container train as a factor in improving safety and efficiency in intermodal rail transport

Patryk Jurkowski

Integracja komunikacji publicznej w miastach średniej wielkości na przykładzie Pruszkowa
Integration of public transportation in medium-size cities on the example of Pruszków

Wtorek, 3 września 2024 r.

9.00 – 10.30 *Sesja III.3: Problemy decyzyjne i diagnostyczne w systemach logistycznych*

Przewodniczący: Elżbieta Macioszek, Jolanta Żak

Sala: Sonata

Sebastian Sobczuk, Anna Borucka, Jakub Liniewski

Diagnostyka procesów produkcyjnych z zastosowaniem wybranych narzędzi Lean Manufacturing
Diagnostics of production processes using selected Lean Manufacturing tools

Maciej Śmieszek

Model integracji wymagań RAMS w procesie inwestycyjnym związanym z zaprojektowaniem i wykonaniem podsystemu „Sterowanie – urządzenia przytorowe”

Integration model of RAMS requirements in the investment process related to design and implementation of the “Control command and signalling subsystem – trackside”

Ludmiła Filina-Dawidowicz, Wojciech Durczak, Péter Ákos Szilassy

Proces decyzyjny związany z planowaniem lądowo-morskich łańcuchów transportowych żywności w kontenerach chłodniczych z uwzględnieniem wpływu czynników ryzyka

Decision-making process related to planning of land-sea transport chains of food in refrigerated containers taking into account risk factors’ impact

Sławomir Tkaczyk

Problematyka zabezpieczania ładunków spaletyzowanych folią stretch
Problems of securing palletized loads with stretch film

10:45 – 12:00 *Sesja plenarna III*

Przewodniczący: Jacek Pielecha, Konrad Lewczuk

Sala: Scherzo

Renata Żochowska

Identyfikacja miejsc krytycznych w sieci transportowej - ujęcie systemowe
Identification of critical sites in the transport network - systemic approach

Mirosław Siemieżyk

Analiza metod oceny ryzyka zagrożeń cyberbezpieczeństwa w systemach IT i OT stosowanych w transporcie.
An analysis of methods for assessing the risk of cybersecurity threats in IT and OT systems used in transportation

Michał Grzybowski, Jakub Młyńczak, Lucyna Sokółowska

Opis zależności przebiegowych dla komputerowych systemów srk

Description of route dependencies for computer-based railway signalling systems

Dariusz Pyza, Tomasz Krukowicz, Krzysztof Firląg, Milena Gołofit-Stawińska

Wyznaczanie trójkątów widoczności z wykorzystaniem danych z lotniczego skaningu laserowego
Determining visibility triangles using airborne laser scanning data

